

NANO-SCALE REINFORCEMENT FOR HIERARCHICAL AEROSPACE COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Radial growth of carbon nanotubes (CNT) on structural composite fibers forms a “fuzzy fiber” reinforced plastic (FFRP) hierarchical architecture that has been shown to improve inter-, intra-laminar, and multifunctional properties of filamentary composites through both theoretical and empirical analyses. Despite many efforts to implement this nano-scale architecture onto high performance carbon fibers (CF), the synthesis of CNT on CFs has resulted in large fiber and composite in-plane strength reductions by as much as 60%. We utilize a novel and scalable dip-coat process for high-yield low-temperature CNT growth on CFs that preserves microfiber properties as shown from previous single fiber level testing. Unidirectional ply-level testing of fuzzy carbon fiber reinforced plastic (fuzzy CFRP) was conducted and revealed preservation of in-plane mechanical properties. Moreover, the successful scale-up to laminated fuzzy carbon fiber reinforced plastic (fuzzy CFRP) laminates is presented here, demonstrating the scalability of the CNT synthesis methodology, and the potential for ubiquitous nano-scale matrix reinforcement for interlaminar property improvements while retaining in-plane laminate properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

The direct growth of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) on carbon fibers (CFs) has been of great interest to enable a hierarchical nano-engineered aerospace composite with enhanced interlaminar properties [1]. However, many past efforts have been met with challenges in CNT growth catalyst adhesion and fiber strength loss incurred through typical chemical vapour deposition (CVD) processes employed [2]. Previous studies have shown fiber surface damage arising from interactions with metal catalyst particles at high CNT growth temperatures in excess of 700 °C [3]. Additionally, heat treatments of CFs above a threshold temperature have also been observed to degrade fiber properties even in inert environments [4]. A recent study reports the use of non-covalent functionalization of the CF surface and the implementation of a low temperature CVD growth in the fabrication of ply-level fuzzy carbon fiber reinforced plastic (fuzzy CFRP) with preserved in-plane properties [5]. A summary of the published study is presented here along with recent scale-up to laminate level synthesis.

2 METHODS

2.1 Catalyst deposition and CNT Growth

A non-covalent functional coating 0.25 wt% Potassium Poly(styrene-alt-[dipotassium maleate]) (K-PSMA) was synthesized here by modifying the method described by Stroock et al [6]. Unsized

TohoTenax HTR40 24K carbon fiber tows [7] were dip-coated in the functional coating for 5 min and dried in a vacuum oven at ~ 80 °C and -91 kPa for 5 min. The functionalized tow was then dip-coated in a 0.05 M catalyst solution of $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in isopropanol and dried a second time in the vacuum oven under the same conditions. Subsequently, tows were inserted into a quartz tube furnace (25 mm outer diameter, 22 mm inner diameter, 30 cm length inside a Lindberg/Blue M Minimite) and subjected to a low temperature $\text{CO}_2/\text{C}_2\text{H}_2$ chemical vapour deposition process [8] at 480 °C detailed in the corresponding publication [5].

2.2 Unidirectional Composite Processing

CNT-grown tows were removed from the furnace and inserted into an epoxy resin infusion mold, which forms a channel around the tow. The assembly was vacuum bagged and connected to an aerospace epoxy resin (Hexcel RTM6 [9]) source on the inlet end of the mold, and to a vacuum source on the outlet end. After the setup was heated to 90 °C, resin flow valves were opened gradually to allow the resin to infuse through the full length of the channel / tow. The setup was cured at 160 °C for 75 min and 180 °C for 120 min. After cooling, the infusion setup was disassembled and the unidirectional composite removed from the mold. The specimens were then tabbed in accordance with the ASTM D4018 [10] standard with a gauge length of 150 mm. Baseline composite specimens were similarly fabricated by directly impregnating as-received HTR40 carbon fiber tows. Resulting baseline and fuzzy CFRP specimens have $\sim 67\%$ fiber volume fraction, allowing results to be directly compared with aerospace composites.

2.3 Woven Laminated Composite Processing

Desized aerospace grade HTA40 3K fibers were dip-coated in K-PSMA functional coating for 5 min and dried in a vacuum oven at ~ 80 °C and -91 kPa for 5 min. Functionalized fabrics were then dip-coated in a 0.05 M catalyst solution of $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in isopropanol before being vacuum dried in the same conditions previously described. Weaves were subjected to a similar low temperature CVD process as implemented on the tows. CNT-grown weaves were then laid up between two plates (lined with flow media), vacuum bagged, and then connected to vacuum and Hexcel RTM6 resin sources on opposite ends. The setup was heated to 90 °C, infused with resin, and left to cure at 160 °C for 75 min and 180 °C for 120 min. Specimens were subsequently removed from the bagging to yield a fuzzy CFRP woven laminate.

2.4 Mechanical Testing

Tensile testing of 5 baseline and 5 fuzzy CFRP unidirectional specimens was conducted on an Instron 1332 load frame (220 kN capacity) at a displacement rate of 1 mm/min in accordance with ASTM D4018 [10]. Optical strain mapping was employed to measure the strain during loading through specimen failure.

Figure 1: Scanning electron micrograph of CNT growth on CF tows prior to resin infusion (a) and unidirectional fuzzy CFRP specimens fabricated after infusing resin through fuzzy CF tows and tabbing sample ends (b).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Scanning electron microscopy conducted on CVD processed tows reveals highly conformal and radial growth of CNTs with lengths of 1-2 microns around individual carbon fibers across the area of the tows, pointing to the homogeneous catalyst adhesion over the fiber surface. Stress values were calculated by dividing the load by the composite cross-sectional area, and composite chord modulus values were calculated from the slope of the stress-strain curve between the strain limits of 1000 and 6000 microstrains [10].

Figure 2: Longitudinal composite chord modulus values (a) and composite strength values (b) indicate no change in stiffness and strength with the radial growth of CNT on CF tows.

Figure 2a shows that the longitudinal composite modulus was unchanged with the addition of radial CNTs since CNTs are oriented perpendicular to the longitudinal direction of the CFs and consequently

do not significantly change the longitudinal stiffness of the epoxy matrix [11]. Additionally, the underlying CF modulus is expected to be unchanged based on previous single fiber testing studies conducted with the presented CNT growth method [12].

More importantly, longitudinal composite strength was preserved as shown in Figure 2b, which is in large contrast to the significant fiber degradation previously observed through other CNT growth processing on CF [2]. This result is highly consistent with single fiber testing data, which showed retention of fiber tensile properties utilizing the presented technique of non-covalent functionalization and low temperature CVD processing. As a result, this process is shown to preserve the highly desired in-plane properties of CFRP, while integrating CNT reinforcement along the transverse direction, demonstrated as toughening the interlaminar and interlaminar regions [1].

Furthermore, this advancement motivates the scale-up of the described process to the fabrication of a fuzzy CFRP at the laminate level. Scanning electron micrographs (Fig. 3a) of CVD processed aerospace weaves also shows successful and conformal CNT growth analogous to that seen on tows, and demonstrates the scalability of this incipient wetness method. Additionally, fuzzy CFRP woven laminates were successfully manufactured with uniform thickness and control over fiber volume fraction of ~50% (Fig. 3b). This processing will thus pave the way for a host of needed laminate-level mechanical and multifunctional characterization studies to directly measure the interlaminar property enhancements of the fuzzy CFRP architecture, while retaining in-plane composite properties.

Figure 3: Scanning electron micrograph of radial CNT growth on aerospace CF weave prior to epoxy resin infusion (a) and cured fuzzy CFRP 3-ply woven laminate (b).

4 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

A new method for enabling radial CNT growth on CF is presented that enables ubiquitous nano-scale matrix reinforcement in the composite, while circumventing the drastic reductions of in-plane strengths previously reported in the literature. Unidirectional composite testing empirically demonstrates its efficacy in preserving in-plane strength and stiffness at the ply level. The scalability of the CNT synthesis methodology was also successfully demonstrated on aerospace CF weaves, which were infused with epoxy resin to manufacture fuzzy CFRP laminates that will be the subject of continuing work for critical laminate-level characterizations. This capability will enable direct measurements of interlaminar mechanical enhancements through mode I fracture toughness and short beam shear strength testing, as well as electrical / thermal conductivity improvements.

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